

FACTOR OF INFLUENCE OF HYGIENIC HEALTH- IMPROVING TECHNOLOGIES IN ENSURING YOUTH HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Maintaining the health of the younger generation, including student youth, has been and remains one of the most important social problems of society. The main task of student youth is to replenish the number of qualified members of society. It is obvious that training highly qualified specialists is possible only when they have good mental and somatic health. Students are especially susceptible to the impact of negative environmental factors, since entering a university places a young person in new living conditions to which they must adapt. In addition, the learning process is accompanied by high emotional and mental stress.

ФАКТОР ВЛИЯНИЯ ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКИХ ОЗДРАВЛИВАЮЩЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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ABSTRACT

Сохранение здоровья молодого поколения, в том числе студенческой молодежи, было и остается одной из важнейших социальных проблем общества. Основная задача студенческой молодежи – пополнение числа квалифицированных членов общества. Очевидно, что подготовка высококвалифицированных специалистов возможна лишь тогда, когда они имеют хорошее психическое и соматическое здоровье. Студенчество особенно подвержено воздействию отрицательных факторов окружающей среды, так как поступление в вуз ставит молодого человека в новые условия жизни, к которым необходимо

адаптироваться. Кроме того, процесс обучения сопровождается высокими эмоциональными и умственными нагрузками.

YOSHLAR SALOMATLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA GIGIENIK SALOMATLIK- TEXNOLOGIYALARINING TA'SIR OMILI

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ABSTRACT

Yosh avlod, jumladan, o'quvchilar salomatligini asrash jamiyatning eng muhim ijtimoiy muammolaridan biri bo'lib kelgan va shunday bo'lib qoladi. Talaba yoshlarning asosiy vazifasi jamiyatning malakali a'zolarini ko'paytirishdan iborat. O'z-o'zidan ko'rinib turibdiki, yuqori malakali mutaxassislarni tayyorlash ularning ruhiy va jismoniy salomatligi yaxshi bo'lgandagina mumkin bo'ladi. Talabalar atrof-muhitning salbiy omillariga ayniqsa sezgir, chunki universitetga kirish yosh odamni moslashishi kerak bo'lgan yangi yashash sharoitlariga olib keladi. Bundan tashqari, o'quv jarayoni yuqori hissiy va ruhiy stress bilan birga keladi.

In Uzbekistan, youth health is considered an investment in the main resource of social development of the country. Such attention of the state to this issue becomes obvious when paying attention to the specific weight of the young generation (up to 60%) among the population of the country. Thus, the tasks of studying and developing ways aimed at forming the health of the young generation in Uzbekistan are a priority and urgent.

The aim of the research is to scientifically substantiate hygienic health-saving technologies in ensuring the health of young people. To achieve the goal, the following research tasks were set: To establish hygienic tools for health-saving technologies for young people in educational institutions.

The object of the study was organized groups of young men from educational institutions in the amount of 390 people. Materials of medical registration forms. Daily menu-layouts. Questionnaires of medical and social studies. Results and conclusions Modern studies have established that 20-25% of students in schools, lyceums and colleges were not harmoniously developed, the appeal for medical help for illnesses ranged from 39% to 49%, 8-16% of adolescents had a body weight deficit [4]. According to the Institute of Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the overall incidence of adolescents aged 15-17 increased by 20.8% from 2013 to 2015 [3]. Unfavorable changes in the health of young people cause enormous social and economic damage, often causing professional restrictions when choosing professions and employment. A set of programs is being implemented in the republic, the

fundamental goal of which is to create prerequisites for the emergence of a conscious need in 127 young people to improve their physical health, engage in physical education and sports. When asked whether the respondent considers his lifestyle healthy, more than 93% of young men answered positively. At the same time, when determining the place of physical culture in the life of pre-conscription youth, based on the analysis of the structure of free time, it was revealed that urban young men prefer to relax with friends, listen to music, take additional classes, and play computer games (up to 60%). A less representative group of young men in their free time visit discos, cafes, relax with their families, and participate in "small business". And only 20.4% regularly play sports, are involved in the physical culture movement, and work in garden plots. At the same time, when determining the place of physical culture in the life of pre-conscription youth, based on the analysis of the structure of free time, it was revealed that urban young men prefer to relax with friends, listen to music, take additional classes, and play computer games (up to 60%). A less representative group of young men in their free time visit discos, cafes, relax with their families, and participate in "small business". And only 20.4% regularly play sports, are involved in the physical culture movement, and work in garden plots. The degree of involvement of pre-conscripts in physical education and sports activities is influenced by both objective and subjective factors. Among the objective reasons, the most important are limited material availability of sports complexes for mass physical education and sports; irrational use of material and technical equipment in the system of physical education in educational institutions; orientation and selection of children and adolescents for "big-time sports"; negative attitude of parents to the sport chosen by the teenager, employment with additional academic load and work activities, etc. The degree of involvement of pre-conscripts in physical education and sports activities is influenced by both objective and subjective factors. Among the objective reasons, the most important are limited material availability of sports complexes for mass physical education and sports; irrational use of material and technical equipment in the system of physical education in educational institutions; orientation and selection of children and adolescents for "big-time sports"; negative attitude of parents to the sport chosen by the teenager, employment with additional academic load and work activities, etc. A comprehensive assessment of the physical status of young men of the conscription resource revealed: • 19.3% of young men in lyceums had a development level below average and 0.3% had low indicators of physical development; • the Quetelet index, which characterizes the nutritional status of practically healthy young men of 17 years of age, varies within the range of 19.1-22.3, and its average values are within the reference values of the ratio of height and body weight, but were close to their lower limit. a comparative analysis of the physical activity of young men from various educational institutions showed a reliable decrease among young men from academic lyceums compared to their peers from the military lyceum, which was reflected accordingly in their daily energy requirements. Considering the fact of a close relationship between a person's nutritional status and his or her morbidity [1; 2], we analyzed the relationship and direction of the influence of consumed nutrients on the morbidity of young men. When studying the structure of morbidity, attention was primarily paid to groups of diseases caused by malnutrition, such as alimentary 128 dystrophies, metabolic disorders, vitamin deficiency, and diseases of the digestive system. An assessment of the actual diet showed that it was inadequate to the

energy needs of young men in academic lyceums, and that it was unbalanced in the main ingredients with a pronounced carbohydrate focus. A study of the influence of the nature of nutrition on alimentary-dependent morbidity in young men revealed a connection between individual food ingredients and individual pathologies of the digestive system. Thus, a strong direct correlation was found between cholecystitis and: sugar consumption ($r=+0.68$; $p<0.01$); a direct correlation of medium density with the consumption of proteins ($r=+0.58$; $p<0.01$) and animal fats ($r=+0.44$; $p<0.01$). Research has proven that the nutritional status of young men in lyceums is assessed as low and, based on a combination of indicators, this contingent belongs to the "risk group". At the same time, when conducting a comprehensive assessment of the nutritional status of the pupils of the military lyceum - school Temurbekov, it was found that in the structure of physical activity Temurbekov the share of high physical activity is 1.5 times higher than that of young men from educational lyceums. Moreover, 55.7% of pupils had average physical development, 44.3% - high physical development; 77.5% of young men belonged to the I health group and 20.5% of individuals had various functional and morphological deviations (II health group). The results of a comprehensive assessment of the nutritional status of military lyceum students showed that properly organized actual nutrition according to a single, balanced food set in combination with a controlled level of physical activity helps maintain health and reduces the risk of developing nutritionally dependent pathology.

Conclusions. Thus, the complex of measures is considered as one of the hygienic directions of health-saving medical and preventive technologies, and is one of the hygienic links of the systemic medical approach in the implementation of oriented tasks in the formation of health of young men.

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